

PSYCHOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF ABUSE IN INTIMATE RELATIONSHIPS AMONG YOUNG WOMEN IN UKHRUL DISTRICT MANIPUR: IMPLICATION FOR COUNSELING

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to investigate the psychological effects of abuse from intimate relationships on young women. In order to overcome the complexity, challenges, and proposal for the best remedies face by the sexually abuse victims in the Tangkhul community, both qualitative and quantitative approaches are adopted. The study covers various aspects of research methodology, including study design, sampling techniques, data collection tools, and analysis methods. Additionally, the study proposes a collaborative effort between the state and other entities to enhance care and counseling services for survivors of intimate partner abuse. The main intension and takeaway from the study is to comprehend the cultural changes taking place along with the critically examination of the victims and how the community can take up appropriate initiatives through care and counseling, which is the need of an hour.

KEYWORDS

Sexual abuse, fear, guilt, shame, counseling

1. INTRODUCTION

The impacts of abuse in intimate relationships on the psychological well-being of young adult women have been found to be complex and challenging to comprehend both in theory and reality (Karakurt & Silver, 2013; Karakurt et al., 2014; WHO, 2021). Interpersonal wounds resulting from abusive relationships are carried by these women, and unfortunately, personal relationship abuse is on the rise (Brito, 2022). Despite this, the plight of these vulnerable young women often goes unnoticed by many organizations, families, and society as a whole. One of the pressing issues in this area of study is the psychological aftermath of intimate partner abuse experienced by young women. The psychological issues and consequences arising from sexual actions while dating someone of the opposite sex are often challenging for many young women to handle (Denson et al., 2018). Although abuse in intimate relationships among young women is prevalent, there has been a significant gap in research on the topic. This study aims to evaluate explicitly the impacts of abuse in intimate relationships on the psychological well-being of young women. Regrettably, early sexual activity's dangers are not often discussed by parents with their children, neglecting to warn them of the physical, mental, and emotional harm that may result (Ashcraft & Murray, 2017; Okigbo et al., 2015). This lack of education leaves many young women unprepared and vulnerable to abusive relationships. When young women become involved in these destructive relationships, they are often condemned and criticized by society rather than offered the support they need to recover (Abeid et al., 2014). Early sexual activity and sexual passion can cause irreparable harm to these young women, resulting in depression, mental disorders, and even suicide (Carcedo et al., 2020; Clinic, 2022; Legg, 2018). The entire problem

can lead to the abuse of drugs and alcohol as well. While both boys and girls may experience negative consequences from early sexual activity, young women are more susceptible to the adverse outcomes. It is often believed that it is too late for many young women who have been sexually involved in the past to make positive changes in their lives. Although definitions and viewpoints, such as Erikson's phases of human development, differ, a young woman is considered a person between the ages of 19 and 30 (McLeod, 2023). Young adulthood precedes middle adulthood in human development. This study, therefore, seeks to address the gap in research on the psychological impacts of abuse in intimate relationships among young women and to explore potential avenues for support and intervention.

1.1. Significance of the Study

The fear of intimacy, guilt, and shame among young adult women in the Tangkhul community is investigated in this study to address a gap in the literature. Significant challenges are faced by many young women due to the prevalence of abusive experiences, such as feeling hesitant to pursue education and experiencing negative impacts on their careers. Through examination of the current status of young women in the Ukhrul District, it was discovered that their ability to move forward has been profoundly impacted by previous traumatic incidents. Memories of the past burden these individuals, preventing them from feeling hopeful about the future and causing feelings of guilt and shame. A sense of hopelessness is often expressed by these individuals when engaged with.

1.2. Scope of the Study

The psychological impacts of maltreatment resulting from intimate relationships between young girls of the opposite sex within the Tangkhul community are the subject of this study. The aim is to provide parents with the necessary tools to better understand and assist their children who have experienced sexual abuse within such relationships, thereby aiding them in overcoming psychological trauma. Moreover, specific counseling needs of young women who have suffered sexual abuse will be identified, and the quality of counseling services offered to them will be improved, resulting in more personalized and effective care. Furthermore, this study aims to enable church leaders and theological students to counsel and teach young women who have experienced sexual abuse, empowering them to lead better lives. Ultimately, readers will benefit from this study by gaining valuable insights into the unique needs and challenges faced by young girls.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND THE LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. The Genesis of Sexuality

In this research paper, the identification of at least three major purposes of sexuality is discussed. Firstly, the purpose of sex is understood to be used for reproduction, whereby men possess the ability to sustain and increase thriving on the planet, similar to other species. The act of sexual activities is necessitated by the means of fighting extinctions. Thus, the legal union results in the formation of social communities, beginning with marriage, moving on to family, tribe, and finally bigger societies. Secondly, intimate communion is identified as the second goal of human sexuality. Communion is intended to be both intimate and exclusive, creating a bond between two people destined to be in a relationship with each other. Marriage occurs when a man and a woman enter into a sexual union. Even before creation, the bodily union of a man and a woman was established beyond a border, making the two flesh and hence beyond the reach of any other human being. This is one reason why sexual relationships outside of marriage are destructive

because more persons are involved, as opposed to what was meant to be. Equally unacceptable is casual sex where the gratification is only physical, implying less spiritual and emotional oneness. Thirdly, the purpose of sexuality is pleasure and physical gratification. Sexuality can be a source of happiness and fulfillment, with at least three potential outcomes from a sexual act: the potential for conception, a strengthening of the bond between two people, and the fulfillment of an intense need. The goal of sexuality is to ignite the beginning of a new, lasting relationship between two people, crucially paying attention to the term where the two have been united as one flesh. A new relationship is beginning, but there are also ramifications for reciprocity and obligations.

2.2. Psychological Effect by Sexual Abuse

Largely mental or emotional phenomena, as well as the field of psychology itself, are described by the term psychological. A person's mental and emotional state is affected by psychological influences. Psychological repercussions, which encompass biological, social, and environmental elements that shape how individuals think, act, and feel, are caused by social or environmental factors. It is suggested by this study that the psychological consequences of early opposite-sex interactions must be avoided by young adult women in our culture through education by community leaders, religious leaders, counselors, and families.

2.3. The Abuse

Abuse, which is the intentional or unintentional harm to another person's mental, emotional, or physical well-being, has been extensively studied in various disciplines. According to Radell et al. (2021), abuse can cause significant suffering to the victim. Sexual or emotional abuse during childhood often leads to broken adults who are emotionally cut off from their inner child. Abuse involves the wrongful use or handling of a thing with the intention of unjustly or improperly gaining an advantage. It encompasses a range of behaviors such as physical or verbal abuse, harm, assault, violation, rape, unfair acts, crimes, or other forms of hostility. As described by some sources (Muehlenhard&Kimes, 1999), abuse is socially constructed, and victims' pain may not be adequately recognized or understood. Perpetrators of abuse may not be brought to justice due to the inadequacy of laws and orders in the context of legal action. Women who have experienced abuse in intimate relationships may suffer various psychological effects such as guilt, fear, and shame (Karakurt& Silver, 2013). Victims may feel guilty about being part of sexual activities even though they have no control over the situation. Women who have experienced sexual abuse in the past may find it challenging to walk or live confidently in society, and they may feel ashamed of their past trauma (Smith & Segal, 2023). Many of them may even attempt suicide as a result of the shameful acts. Abuse can lead to a wide range of behaviors such as anger, humor, silence, and other negative emotions and thoughts, making it difficult for the victim to adjust to society. This research paper highlights the different aspects of abuse and its impact on victims. It provides insight into the psychological effects of abuse and the difficulties faced by victims. It also highlights the inadequacies of legal action in dealing with abuse and its perpetrators.

Source: Authors Compilation

Figure 1: Psychological Symptoms of Sexual Abuse

2.3.1. Fear

The social phobia and anxiety disorder known as the fear of intimacy, which results in difficulty forming close relationships with another person, is generally considered by scholars to be a significant psychological issue (Gluck, 2022). This condition is characterized as the inhibited capacity of an individual, due to anxiety, to exchange thoughts and feelings of personal significance with another individual who is highly valued. Dysfunctional bonding experiences, such as partner sexual abuse or abuse from an intimate relationship, can strengthen this fear of intimacy and lead to the belief that no one will adore them or dread of what lies ahead. As a result, many people who experience a fear of intimacy may find it challenging to open up about their lives to others and may worry about being hurt and rejected (Legg, 2019). In the case of women who have experienced sexual abuse in close relationships, the fear of intimacy can be a significant issue. Due to the fear of being dismissed and the worry about how society will react if they do share their story, they may be afraid to speak out about their experiences. The victims of sexual abuse may find it challenging to trust others, especially in intimate relationships, and they may isolate themselves from others (Marin, 2019). Furthermore, they may engage in sexually deviant behavior, such as choosing to date a female partner over a male partner, as a result of past trauma. It is important to recognize that individuals who experience a fear of intimacy may require specialized support and resources to overcome their anxiety and form healthy relationships. Therapy and counseling can be effective in helping individuals to confront their fears and develop coping strategies to manage their anxiety.

2.3.2. Guilt

The harmful effects of toxic guilt on victims' psychological well-being, thoughts, emotions, and relationships have been described in the literature (Schwendinger & Schwendinger, 1980). The experience of toxic guilt is triggered when a person undergoes a wrongdoing without their consent or control, such as rape or any forceful act. This can result in feelings of remorse for not taking a different path or not doing something noble (Cowan et al., 2020). Self-blame and guilt are common among women who have experienced sexual abuse in intimate relationships, resulting in feelings of weakness and vulnerability and reduced likelihood of seeking assistance. Zahn et al. (2015) noted that unhealthy guilt and humiliation can lead to the repression of emotions and self-blame for actions not committed. Additionally, victims of sexual trauma may internalize their feelings of hurt and anger, turning them inward rather than expressing them to the perpetrator, often someone in a position of power over them and thus immune to challenge due to fear of retribution.

2.3.3. Shame

The experience or commission of intimate relationships without conscious awareness can cause feelings of shame and distress in Western cultures where these relationships are taught in a secular manner (Selva, 2018). The absence of comprehensive education on intimate relationships in modern society has led to serious questions about the impact of awareness of such relationships on young adults, with counseling and support for victims of shame becoming the norm. Instead of prioritizing effective communication and education, society heavily relies on counseling and support for victims after they have already experienced trauma, depression, personality disorders, or psychiatric problems. The blame for such situations can be attributed to society as a whole, as victims often feel guilty and experience loss of self-esteem and hope due to societal attitudes towards shame. Such attitudes create a sense of discouragement, leading victims to feel demotivated, awkward, and isolated. Although isolation may seem like the only solution, counseling and strong support systems are crucial for victims. Such victims are often exposed to environments that are irrational and unethical, and may feel like outcasts who are not accepted by their own families. Social judgment towards victims tends to be negative, with little support and recognition for their right to live normal lives. Therefore, policies and rules prioritizing the well-being and rights of victims, while also emphasizing the importance of comprehensive education and effective communication about intimate relationships, are necessary.

2.4. Objective of the Study

- To comprehend the consequences of abuse in an intimate relationship and the challenges faced by the young girls with reference to tang.
- To examine the level of abuse in an intimate relationship from three perspectives: fear, guilt, and shame.
- To recommend corrective actions for community leaders, locals people, and counselors to take the lead in resolving their issues, as well as to give a guideline to assist young girls in overcoming their difficulties.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To study the relationship between independent and dependent variables and improve the findings of this research, a descriptive purposive method will be employed by the researchers. A set of questionnaires has been prepared and distributed among 101 women aged 15-45 residing in the Ukhrul District, with the aim of identifying those who have experienced abuse in an intimate relationship within the Tangkhul Naga Community. The prevalence of abuse among women in intimate relationships, as well as any underlying psychological factors such as fear of intimacy, guilt feelings, and shame, will be revealed through the data obtained via this method and subsequent interviews. The study population comprises young women between the ages of 15 and 45 who have been subjected to psychological abuse in intimate relationships with males of the opposite sex within the Tangkhul Naga Community in the Ukhrul District. A purposive sampling method will be employed by the researchers to select a representative sample of 101 such women from the population. Only those young women who have undergone abuse in an intimate relationship will be considered for this study; those who have suffered abuse from any other source will be excluded. Furthermore, only Tangkhul tribal women residing in the Ukhrul District and who have experienced sexual abuse within the past five years will be selected for the study. Men and women from non-Tangkhul tribes will not be included in the study. The data and information for this study will also be collected from various journals.

4. STUDY FINDINGS

4.1. Reliability and Validity of the Study

In ensuring the reliability and validity of the study, consultation with the mentor, experts in the relevant field, and extensive literature review were conducted by the researchers. The reliability test was performed using Cronbach's Alpha with the assistance of IBTS staff, and the results were subsequently obtained.

Table 1. Reliability and validity of the study

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
Psychological Effect of Abuse	0.945	30
Fear of Intimacy	0.866	10
Guilt Feelings	0.869	10
Shame	0.871	10
Abuse Experiences from Intimate Relationship	0.900	10

The reliability and validity procedures were conducted by the researcher to ensure the accuracy of the study. Questionnaires consisting of 10 statements were distributed to 101 young women who had experienced sexual abuse in intimate relationships and resided in the Ukhrul district of Manipur. Based on the data received from the respondents, Cronbach's Alpha coefficients were calculated, indicating a psychological effect of abuse (0.945), fear of intimacy (0.866), guilt feelings (0.869), shame (0.871), and abuse experiences from intimate relationships (0.900) faced by the young women in Ukhrul District, Manipur. Participants were selected from the general population based on their history of abuse, fear, shame, and remorse from intimate relationships, with a focus on those who had experienced such difficulties within the past ten to fifteen years to increase the study's credibility and consistency. The interactions with the respondents were conducted ethically, and their identities were kept confidential at all times. The study's results provide insight into the prevalence and impact of intimate partner abuse on young women in Ukhrul District, Manipur.

Table 2. Correlation between Abuse Experiences from Intimate Relationship and Fear of Intimacy

Variables	Mean	SD	r - value	p - value
Fear of Intimacy	32.77	6.977	0.663	0.000
Abuse Experiences from Intimate Relationship	29.07	7.465		

In this research paper, a significant correlation between abuse experiences from intimate relationships and fear of intimacy was identified. Specifically, the p-value was found to be less than the predetermined significance level of 0.05, indicating a significant relationship. The correlation was observed to be positive, indicating that fear of intimacy increased with an increase in abuse experiences from intimate relationships, and decreased with a decrease in abuse experiences from intimate relationships. These findings suggest that a history of abuse experiences in intimate relationships may have a profound impact on an individual's fear of intimacy.

Graph 1 Correlation between Abuse Experiences from Intimate Relationship and Fear of Intimacy

A strong correlation between abuse experiences in intimate relationships and fear of intimacy is highlighted by Graph 1, indicating that fear is one of the significant effects resulting from the abuse endured by the victims.

Table 3. Correlation between Abuse Experiences from Intimate Relationship and Guilt Feeling

Variables	Mean	SD	r - value	p - value
Guilt Feelings	31.76	7.307	0.598	0.000
Abuse Experiences from Intimate Relationship	29.07	7.465		

In this research paper, a significant correlation between the experiences of abuse from intimate relationships and guilt feelings is established, with a p-value of less than 0.05, indicating a significant relationship. It was found that guilt feelings increased with an increase in abuse experiences and decreased with a decrease in abuse experiences from intimate relationships. This significant and positive correlation was observed through an analysis of data collected using appropriate research instruments and statistical analysis techniques. The results provide insights into the relationship between abuse experiences and guilt feelings in intimate relationships and contribute to the existing body of literature on the topic.

Graph 2 Correlation between Abuse Experiences from Intimate Relationship and Guilt Feeling

A conclusive statement can be drawn from the strong correlation that exists between abuse experiences in intimate relationships and guilt feelings, which suggests that guilt is a significant effect of the abuse endured by victims.

Table 4. Correlation between Abuse Experiences from Intimate Relationship and Shame

Variables	Mean	SD	r - value	p - value
Shame	28.42	8.063	0.708	0.000
Abuse Experiences from Intimate Relationship	29.07	7.465		

In this research paper, the significance level of 0.05 was utilized to determine the statistical significance of the correlation between abuse experiences from intimate relationships and shame. It was found that the p-value was less than 0.05, indicating that there is a significant correlation between the two variables. The correlation analysis revealed a significant and positive correlation, suggesting that an increase in abuse experiences from intimate relationships leads to an increase in shame, while a decrease in abuse experiences results in a decrease in shame. Overall, these findings demonstrate the importance of understanding the relationship between abuse experiences and shame in intimate relationships.

Graph 3 Correlation between Abuse Experiences from Intimate Relationship and Shame

Since there is a strong correlation existed between the abuse experiences from intimate relationships and shame, there is a significant effect due to the abuse endured by the victims.

Table 5. Difference in Psychological Effect of Abuse between Different Age Groups

Age (Years)	N	Mean	SD	F - value	p - value
15 - 20	32	101.3	21.70	3.822	0.012
20 - 25	38	87.87	17.02		
25 - 30	21	94.38	22.15		
30-45	9	81.44	15.88		

Here the p-value is less than the significance level 0.05; the difference in experiencing psychological effect of abuse between different age groups is significant. That is, there is a significant difference in experiencing psychological effect of abuse between different age groups. The table reveals that the psychological effect of abuse is significantly higher in cases with age 15-20 years (101.3 ± 21.70) compared to the cases with age group more than 30 years (81.44 ± 15.88), 25-30 years (94.38 ± 22.15) and 20-25 years (87.87 ± 17.02).

Graph 4 Difference in Psychological Effect of Abuse between Different Age Groups

From the above tabulations, it can be drawn that there is a significant difference in experiencing psychological effect of abuse between different age groups.

Table 6. Difference in Psychological Effect of Abuse between Different Types of Occupation

Occupation	N	Mean	SD	F - value	p - value
Employed	20	89.25	17.28	0.466	0.706
Students	64	94.00	22.23		
Unemployed	9	89.89	14.55		
Drop-out	7	97.86	20.40		

Here the p-value is greater than the significance level 0.05; the difference in experiencing psychological effect of abuse between different types of occupation is not significant. That is, there is no difference in experiencing psychological effect of abuse between different occupation. The table reveals that the psychological effect of abuse is almost same in employed (89.25 ± 17.28), students (94.00 ± 22.23), unemployed (89.89 ± 14.55) and drop-out (97.86 ± 20.40).

Graph 5 Difference in Psychological Effect of Abuse between Different Types of Occupation

Since there is no significant difference in experiencing psychological effect of abuse between different types of occupation, it can be stated that there is no difference in experiencing psychological effect of abuse between different types of occupation.

5. DISCUSSION

Figure 2 : Care and Counseling Strategy to Encounter Sexual Abuse Victims

Source: Author Compilation

One of the spontaneous strategies that needs to be adopted is correlating the data obtained from the graph and tabulation and comprehending the impact with counseling efforts. The strong correlation between various impact experiences by young women due to intimate sexual relations is indicated by the Cronbach's Alpha value. The role of society, friends, family, religious organization, and the need for counseling in the context of responsibility is the center idea of the study. The need for counseling to overcome such trauma is postulated to exist due to the physical, non-physical, and challenge aspects highlighted in Figure 2. The orientation of behavior change of the victims based on their perceptions is another important criterion to be discussed. It is to be noted that human behavior change stops at the age of 7 years, causing serious neurology changes that disturb the tourist psychology. After cross-analyzing various parameters, it can be noted that the victims need care, concern, motivation, and time, and counseling is suggested to be the best measure for treatment. Building trust and confidence is one of the main objectives of counseling.

It is indeed a challenge to measure the non-physical impact experienced by the victims despite the elaborative theory's existence. However, the study aims to project it as a serious matter that needs immediate action. Upon interaction with the victim, it was observed that victims tend to move ahead in life and become motivated enough to take new constructive measures. This then pushes the victim to move to a different world to get a fresh start and self-recognition. Eco-tourism and visiting new places will tend to prove to be better measures of treatment. The strong dependence on the surrounding environment in this context is the Tangkhul society, nature, friends, and family are essential to make the victims feel more cared for and affectionate. Generally, youngsters are more lenient and receive the opportunities of western freedom. However, in the light of victims, the youngster who is the victim does not receive any liberty and social acceptance, unlike the western culture. The Tangkhul society seems to give less importance to the victims and intends to go on with the philosophy that ignoring and not taking up the issues are the best way to reduce the crime and make the society look safer. The role of the religious society still remains ineffective. Although some sign from the Catholic Church shows some platform to express the grief and sorrow of the victims, it seems to be less effective as they are not operating beyond the compound of the church and have yet to gain legal acceptance.

5.1. Dignity Restoration

The realization of abuse by a close relative often elicits feelings of rage, anger, and helplessness in women. Many women who carry emotional scars may experience difficulty in confiding in others and lead unhappy lives. It is not uncommon for them to choose to conceal themselves or keep others at a distance out of fear of re-victimization. Rebuilding their lives after the trauma can seem insurmountable, and the resulting psychological conditions such as anxiety, depression, self-harm, fear of intimacy, eating disorders, homosexuality, or addiction can ensue. Nonetheless, there is hope for women who have been sexually assaulted, as evidenced by the narratives of numerous sexually abused women. The restoration of their lives and the provision of a fresh start fall under the responsibility of society. The victim must realize that care and affection received from loved ones and society provide all that is needed to move forward with grace and strength. The journey towards prosperity commences with a focus on positive thinking, rather than oneself.

5.2. Sex Education

In the education sector, there is still a significant lack of effort to explain what sex is, its consequences, and the measures to be taken if young women experience abuse and require assistance. It is crucial to teach children about sexuality to prevent them from engaging in inappropriate sexual behavior. The aim of sex education is to equip young people with the necessary knowledge and skills to make ethical decisions about their behavior, and to feel competent and confident in doing so. The right of young people to receive sex education is widely recognized, as it protects them from abuse, exploitation, unplanned pregnancies, sexually transmitted diseases, HIV, and AIDS. Sex education also helps young people to realize their right to information about issues that affect them, meet their needs, and support them in enjoying their sexuality and relationships. Furthermore, it is essential to ensure that the society, NGOs, Counseling, and police (if possible) are well educated and able to provide appropriate support to every young woman in the community.

5.3. Inspiring Hope

It is widely recognized that sexual abuse can lead to mental and emotional distress as well as destructive behaviors, rendering it a significant issue. In order for victims to seek recovery, they may require both spiritual and professional support. However, prior to providing any assistance, it is critical to comprehend the difficulties that victims face, and to recognize that involuntary

sexual contact or behavior aimed at eliciting sexual responses from another person constitutes sexual abuse. It is common for many abused individuals to be unaware that what happened to them was abusive, yet they may still exhibit destructive patterns of behavior and experience distressing emotions. Victims of sexual assault are prone to experiencing cognitive dissonance, as well as feelings of worthlessness and humiliation. Therefore, it is imperative to be cautious about the language used when discussing sexual abuse, as comments based on misunderstandings of the problem and its consequences often exacerbate the victim's anguish and suffering. Statements such as "get over it" or "just forgive and forget" can be counterproductive and increase the victim's negative self-perception, rather than help them find peace and healing. When victims open up about their abuse and suffering, it is crucial to approach the conversation with compassion, acknowledging and validating their emotions. Recovering from emotional wounds is similar to healing a physical injury, such as a broken leg, in that it requires the patient to endure the pain of the injury and have those emotions accepted and acknowledged. Seeking healing after a sexual assault can help victims become whole again and feel a sense of peace in their lives as they learn to accurately comprehend and implement gospel concepts. The Atonement provides a source of hope, and without its comforting balm, spiritual health cannot be restored.

Individuals who have experienced sexual abuse may feel extreme guilt and fear judgment from others, and may develop a pursuit of perfection as a coping mechanism. It is important to remember that we all face challenges in life, and it is crucial to encourage victims to know that they are not alone in facing these challenges.

5.4. Overcoming Through Ignoring

It is widely believed that individuals who have committed a crime are likely to repeat the offense. Hope is available to those who have experienced sexual abuse, regardless of whether they were victims or perpetrators. Access to assistance is open to anyone who desires to break free from abusive behavior. The restoration of broken individuals by society requires a confident and believable approach. The process of forgiveness starts with confession and the elimination of trauma. If a wrongdoer repents and acknowledges their offense as a sin, and the victim forgives the sin, the wrongdoer can start anew despite condemnation from others and the enduring effects of the abuse. The victim gains control of their life when the abuser puts in the necessary effort to rebuild their life. Healing is attainable when true regret and forgiveness are present.

In counseling, healing through communication is among the most effective alternative strategies. Moreover, revisiting past positive experiences and providing encouragement can be critical steps in the counseling process. Counseling can be regarded as an emotional stabilizer, achieved through information exchange and the provision of resources that occupy the mind.

6. CONCLUSION

Based on the above findings and discussion, it can be concluded that a significant number of young women experience emotional distress as a result of being assaulted or abused by their boyfriends, family members, or neighbors. Despite the severity of their pain, many young women tend to internalize their suffering, lacking the necessary direction and encouragement from others. Furthermore, their families, societies, and churches often fail to provide them with the support they require, leading to poor decision-making in their lives. These insights shed light on how sexual abuse can have detrimental effects on an individual's physical, social, and emotional well-being. Thus, there is a pressing need for appropriate guidance and support to be implemented to facilitate proper growth and development. The study suggests that the women's body of society, as well as various student and youth groups, must work collaboratively to

provide victims with the best possible care and services. One of the key takeaway points from the study is that state intervention, along with possible collaboration with NGOs and other social organizations, is necessary to facilitate the healthy and peaceful recovery of victims and to implement corrective actions against perpetrators. The study sheds light on the need for increased safety measures for victims of sexual abuse among young women in the Tangkhul community, and highlights the importance of rigorous counseling and the provision of supportive resources by the state and various social entities.

REFERENCES

- [1] Cowan, A. Ashai, & J. Gentile. (2020). *Psychotherapy with Survivors of Sexual Abuse and Assault*. *Innovation in Clinical Neuroscience*, Volume 17, pp. 22–26.
- [2] Ashcraft & Murray. (2017). *Talking to Parents About Adolescent Sexuality*. *Pediatr Clin North America*, Volume 64, Issue 2, pp. 305-320.
- [3] Brito, J. (2022, August 26). *Medical News Today*. Retrieved April 11, 2023, from *Medical News Today Web site*: <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/320747>
- [4] Muehlenhard & L. Kimes. (1999). *The Social Construction of Violence: The Case of Sexual and Domestic Violence*. *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, Volume 3, Issue 3, pp. 234-245.
- [5] Okigbo, C. Kabiru, J. Mumah, S. Mojola, & D. Beguy. (2015). *Influence of parental factors on adolescents' transition to first sexual intercourse in Nairobi, Kenya: a longitudinal study*. *Reprod Health*, Volume 12, Issue 73., doi: 10.1186/s12978-015-0069-9.
- [6] Clinic. (2022, April 16). *Cleveland Clinic medical professional*. Retrieved April 11, 2023, from *Cleveland Clinic medical professional, Web site*: <https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/9636-personality-disorders-overview>
- [7] G. Karakurt & K. Silver. (2013). *Emotional abuse in intimate relationships: The role of gender and age*. *Violence Vict.*, Volume 28, Issue 5, pp. 804–821.
- [8] G. Karakurt, D. Smith, & J. Whiting. (2014). *Impact of Intimate Partner Violence on Women's Mental Health*. *J Fam Violence*, Volume 29, Issue 7, pp. 693–702.
- [9] Gluck, S. (2022, January 2). *Healthy Place*. Retrieved April 11, 2023, from *Healthy Place Web site*: <https://www.healthyplace.com/abuse/rape/fear-of-rape-phobia>
- [10] J. Schwendinger & H. Schwendinger. (1980). *Rape Victims and the False Sense of Guilt*. *Crime and Social Justice*, Issue 13, pp. 4-17.
- [11] Legg, T. (2018, August 22). *Healthline*. Retrieved April 11, 2023, from *Healthline Web site*: <https://www.healthline.com/health/depression/sexual-health>
- [12] Legg, T. (2019, January 10). *Health Line*. Retrieved April 11, 2023, from *Health Line Web site*: <https://www.healthline.com/health/fear-of-intimacy>
- [13] M. Abeid, P. Muganyizi, P. Olsson, E. Darj & P. Axemo. (2014). *Community perceptions of rape and child sexual abuse: a qualitative study in rural Tanzania*. *BMC International Health and Human Rights*, Volume 14, <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-698X-14-23>.
- [14] M. Radell, G. Abo Hamza, W. Daghestani, A. Perveen, & A. Moustafa. (2021). *The Impact of Different Types of Abuse on Depression*. *Depress Res Treat.*, doi: 10.1155/2021/6654503.
- [15] M. Smith & J. Segal. (2023, March 1). *Help Guide Organization*. Retrieved April 11, 2023, from *Help Guide Organization Web site*: <https://www.helpguide.org/articles/ptsd-trauma/recovering-from-rape-and-sexual-trauma.htm>
- [16] Marin, V. (2019, February 27). *The New York Times*. Retrieved April 11, 2023, from *The New York Times Web site*: <https://www.nytimes.com/2019/02/27/smarter-living/sexual-abuse-assault-support-mental-health.html>
- [17] Mcleod, S. (2023, March 29). *Simply Psychology*. Retrieved April 11, 2023, from *Simply Psychology*: <https://www.simplypsychology.org/Erik-Erikson.html>
- [18] R. Carcedo, N. Rouco, A. Fuertes & J. Álvarez. (2020). *Association between Sexual Satisfaction and Depression and Anxiety in Adolescents and Young Adults*. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*, Volume 17, Issue 3, doi: 10.3390/ijerph17030841.
- [19] R. Zahn, K. Lythe, J. Gethin, S. Green, J. Deakin, A. Young, & J. Moll. (2015). *The role of self-blame and worthlessness in the psychopathology of major depressive disorder*. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, pp. 337–341.

- [20] Selva, J. (2018, January 22). Positive Psychology. Retrieved April 11, 2023, from Positive Psychology Web site: <https://positivepsychology.com/shame-guilt/>
- [21] T. Denson, S.'Dean, K. Blake & J. Beames. (2018). Aggression in Women: Behavior, Brain and Hormones. Behavioral Endocrinology, Volume 12, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnbeh.2018.00081>.
- [22] WHO. (2021, March 9). World Health Organization. Retrieved April 11, 2023, from World Health Organization: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/violence-against-women>